

Streaming into Language Learning: A Quasi-Experimental Study on Netflix and Vocabulary Acquisition

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ABSTRACT

A significant change has been observed during past few years due to technology advancements in educational and non-educational settings. Netflix, which is considered as one of the best streaming platforms, may not only be used for entertaining purposes but educational purposes as well. As a result of this change, it was speculated that students might have improved their vocabulary after watching Netflix. To achieve this target, a mixed method approach was employed hence sample comprised 50 students who belonged to the sixth, seventh and eighth semesters from the Department of English at National University of Modern Languages Multan Sub-Campus. The theoretical framework adopted in this research was Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985). The results demonstrated positive responses towards the use of Netflix as a language and vocabulary learning tool. In addition to that, some responses showed that it is high time to add Netflix as a language learning tool for teaching and learning processes.

Keywords: Netflix, Digital Learning, Vocabulary Acquisition, English Language

Introduction

Throughout many years, learning English language has always been a quest for non-native speakers. English serves as a global lingua franca and it has become the most important element of everything including education, business, law and entertainment. Learning English as a foreign language was important but now, due to globalization it has become a necessity. Media has so much influence on people and people prefer to watch their favourite shows in English language, even if they are watching the show in their native language, they still prefer to read the subtitles in English. Similarly, English is equally dominant in the field of technology and science. From a human being born, to the introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI), every single thing is introduced

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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and discussed in English due to owing the status of International Language.

A huge paradigm shift has been seen in the field of education; it is noticed that the traditional learning methods which include classroom environment and textbooks to digital learning. Digital learning has been a part of first world countries but it is introduced in other countries for about nine to ten years ago. The classroom environment overall effects the learning of a student, if the class is teacher centred and the teacher is using the old traditional ways to deliver his lecture, the student might feel bored and wants to leave the class therefore, to overcome this issue teachers should upgrade themselves and their teaching methods according to modern day needs. It is very important to have a comfortable environment in learning a language and now thanks to globalization and technological advancements, it has become easier to learn language. Many digital platforms are available and widely accessible to the learners making it easier for them to learn language and new vocabulary through that platform and thus one of those platforms is Netflix. Netflix is considered as the most streamed application for entertainment purposes as it has provided diverse English content.

It is seen that watching Netflix has undoubtedly improved spoken English skills of its viewers but the main question is, whether it has improved their vocabulary as well or not. Watching Netflix for a long period of time may have improved the vocabulary acquisition/learning of the learners, as it provides real-life scenarios and how the native language is used to deal with those cases. It may also help the learners to achieve good vocabulary because of the subtitles, the learners can easily see the word, adopt it and use it in their daily lives. This article investigates the potential impact of Netflix on English language learner's vocabulary.

Background of the study

English is considered as the most spoken language across the globe and demands learning English as a second language (ESL) or English as a Foreign Language (EFL) have been increased due to globalization. English is basically a standard and to fit in this standard, one must know how to communicate in English effectively. Social media is a platform where people from across the globe can gather and share their culture, traditions, norms and customs making language the main medium of this exchange. Not only in business, engineering fields, or entertainment, technological advancements can be noticed in educational sector too. Nowadays, streaming platforms are in spotlight, as the world has become a global village. It is really easy to learn and acquire a different language and for that purpose Netflix is seen as one the best streaming platforms. A student might be unable to listen or speak properly in the target language because of his cultural background, environment, lack of communication and low self-esteem. To practically apply something, a lot of practice is needed and if a student belongs to a non-native English speaking background, his listening and speaking would be adversely affected as he would be unable to practice language properly at his home.

Nowadays, streaming platforms are in spotlight, as the world has become a global village it is really easy to learn and acquire a different language and for that purpose Netflix is seen as one the best streaming platforms. The categorization of different genres has made it easier to acquire a new language because the best way to learn a novel language is through experiencing and analysing real life situations and Netflix provides a large number of those experiences to its viewers where they can enjoy as

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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well as learn new language specifically its vocabulary. One of the main reason Netflix has a strong influence on the vocabulary of its viewer is that it demonstrates the use of vocabulary in daily life scenarios. It basically teaches that how a word is used in a particular context. Students as language learners just cram out a list of vocabulary words without knowing their practical usage but Netflix lets the learner practical implementation on how to use a word in a real- life situations. Another element supporting Netflix's efficiency is the availability of subtitles and multilingual choices, if the learner faces difficulty in understanding the language, he/she can switch to his/her native language or turn on the subtitles to understand the words properly. It can also improve pronunciation and listening abilities because the student becomes familiar with the language and by listening the words again and again his pronunciation and listening gets better. Netflix provides the authentic language exposure to its viewers by using English slangs, idioms and pronunciation of the words in their original language. Netflix provides the basic use of language in various contexts like when to use a formal tone or when to use an informal tone, it also tells the frequency of tone in different contexts like how should a person speak in academic context etc.

Many researches have been done on Netflix and how it can be fruitful in learning and speaking language but a very less research has been conducted empirically on how Netflix helps in vocabulary acquisition. This study focuses on whether Netflix helps English language learners adopt new vocabulary or not.

Literature Review

Literature has shown that when a person begins to learn a new language, s/he is exposed to a variety of words which overall helps them to gain a proper understanding of the words and the meaning they are depicting, and these words are called vocabulary. Vocabulary is basically, a collection or list of words and phrases arranged usually in an alphabetical order and aids in explaining the meaning of something. Staehr (2008) opined that vocabulary building is more inclined towards the reading and writing skills than to speaking and listening skills.

Listening skills are enhanced when learners are repetitively exposed to an audio-visual media. The more they listen to the audios again and again, the better they the get chance to learn new language and to fully acquire it. As the world has digitalized it has become easier to interact with the native speakers and gain knowledge from their work specifically in the filed of English. As non natives have always faced difficulties in learning the English language, now, because of the introduction of many streaming platforms it has become easier to learn language from there. Netflix is announced as the most popular streaming platform which acts as an excellent tool in language learning (Tapper, 2019). The way everything is structured, organized and displayed through the help of words and images in Netflix is exceptional, everything there is giving a meaning, it basically helps in increasing the prior knowledge of the learner about something. Initially, Netflix was a Digital Versatile Disc (DVD) renting platform which provided DVDs be emails till 1997 which by, 2005 got 4.2 million rental subscribers. To ensure the entertainment of its customers and to fulfil the need of the hour in 2007, Netflix announced to charge monthly subscription fee and thus provided all the entertainment through their Personal communication Services(PCs). That's how

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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the comfort of watching one's favourite shows in his house made Netflix a worldwide necessity. Different genres providing different perspectives and vocabulary addressed more viewers making Netflix number five in the rank of most streaming platforms.

Netflix organizes and displays its content in a way that the engagement between the viewer and the content becomes stronger. As Mayer and Johnson (2008), in their Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML) expressed that the visual structures aids in learning language in a more interesting and captivating way. The cognitive theory basically showed how different words, phrases and images combined to give us more in-depth analysis of a particular scene or overall program. The use of vocabulary and sentences along with picture descriptions helped in adding more information in the viewers' previous knowledge. Watching English movies and dramas got teachers more anxious as these genres specifically provides a great help in learning a new language and that too in an excellent way (Srymbetova et al., 2021).

Many linguistic theories are in favour of audio-visual language learning method. One of the best models for SLA was given by Krashen named as Krashen's Input Hypothesis in 1985 which was reviewed by Zixu Luo, he revealed that second language is learned best when the learner is exposed to an input which is slightly greater than his current expertise. His hypothesis has a very significant formula ($I+1$), which indicates that if a learner is exposed to a stimulus, a little bit beyond his knowledge, he will understand and grasp the information more quickly and efficiently. Krashen proposed that productive skills like speaking and writing came as a result of receptive skills (i.e., listening and reading) and if more focus is laid on the productive skills the more enhanced would be the receptive skills. The real-life conversations, debates, use of a bit complex vocabulary in Netflix programs enable the learner to understand language more in depth and also gets an idea on what vocabulary to use in a particular context. Similarly, a learner who watches a Netflix program with subtitles is more likely to adopt new words and learn the English language more easily and effectively than those who just rely on the textbooks (Peter and Webb, 2018). This language learning is called incidental language learning where the learner while watching his favourite English programs along with their subtitles can increase his/her knowledge about the target language. One of the best ways to learn a new language is to listen or talk to the natives and for learners who can't visit the native countries rely on watching the podcasts, programs or documentaries provided in the native language and Netflix being one of the best streaming platforms helps the learners' grasp language and vocabulary whatever they want to.

An English language learner should hold at least a record of 3000-word families to get a grip on spoken discourse (Van Zealand & Schmit, 2013; Web & Rodgers, 2009a, 2009b). Where as to grasp the written discourse, at least 8,000- 9,000 words should be known (Nation, 2006; Schmitt, Jiang & Grabe, 2011). But Webb and Nation, (2017) said that it is nearly impossible to learn this amount of vocabulary in such a short period of classroom time. Several researchers were in favour of extensive reading (Nation, 2015; Schmitt, 2008) but still it is a tedious task to acquire such a great vocabulary from reading only (Cobb, 2007). Therefore, Webb and Rodgers (2009a) assert that if the learner is exposed to L2 television it may play a vital role in learning the language because the words are repeated again and again in a Television (TV) program. This may

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3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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help in retaining more vocabulary in a short span of time. Netflix provides different programs where the learners can easily grasp new vocabulary by watching different types of contents.

When a learner is exposed to multiple representations, s/he is more likely to learn things specially language in a much better way. It is easier to understand a picture, video or a scene if its description is present as revealed by Mayer (1997), that things can be better understood if their explanations are provided not merely through words but through images as well. Basically, if we watch something and listen to the words, phrases or dialogues we can understand that thing very easily for example, a teacher is narrating a story but the students are only listening to it, they may not be able to get the concept the teacher wants to give but on the other hand, if the teacher narrates the story and also provides a picture or video description through multimedia the students would easily be able to grip the concept.

Csikzentmihalyi (1990) considers that as long as the learner knows that his/her task is achievable, s/he can enjoy the process of learning. This attitude is best shown by language learners because whenever they take a class or a language workshop the only thing, they discuss is the overall environment of the class and was it entertaining or boring. Language class fully requires the participants' engagement and if a teacher fails to provide those interesting tasks, the learners are unable to learn anything. Csikzentmihalyi (1995) reveals that a difficult task can arise negative feelings like fear and anxiety among language learners but if those difficulties are tackled effectively, they would result in positive feelings among the language learners. Such joy and ease can help the learners to achieve a beneficial result in their learning. So, it is suggested that the environment of learning has a great impact on language learning and Netflix provides a calm and entertaining environment to learn language particularly its vocabulary.

Statement of the problem

Since the world has revolutionized, still many people do not excess the digital resources. Most of the difficulties are faced by language learners and specifically English language learners in vocabulary acquisition. Gone are the days when learners used to study from the old and traditional classroom methods which only involved word to word translations and rote memorization which only resulted in a large number of good writers and a small number of good English language speakers. This study investigates whether the vocabulary acquisition in English Language Learners increased after watching Netflix. It also investigates whether watching a program in subtitles and dubbing helps in learning new vocabulary and also compares the conventional teaching methods including new and advanced teaching methods and their efficacy.

Present study

This study aims to explore the impact of Netflix on English language learners and to see whether it contributes in acquiring new vocabulary or not.

Objectives

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The research has the following objectives:

To explore the efficiency of Netflix in vocabulary acquisition.

To examine whether it is easy to learn vocabulary through Netflix

To analyse which teaching method is more effective either the traditional one or the advanced one.

To investigate the impact of subtitles and dubbing have on vocabulary acquisition.

Hypothesis

H1: Netflix substantially improves learners' vocabulary acquisition.

Significance of the study

This study is significant because it provides a different way to learn a foreign language marking Netflix as a good learning tool. Learning environment is changed due to the intervention of digital platforms which provide many facilities like providing the viewers with genre selection and language selection making it easier to adopt a new language without wasting hours on cramming the language, its rules and vocabulary. Streaming platforms like Netflix provides a vast variety of regional vocabulary which enables the learners to adopt those words and use them in their daily lives. The main aim of the study is to discuss how to get maximum language and vocabulary learning through Netflix by guiding the English language learners on how to use Netflix in the right way so that it could be beneficial for them. A learner who really wants to improve his English language skills should know how the subtitles and the content work and how they can involve themselves actively in the learning process.

Assumptions

Learners will build a great amount of vocabulary if they watch Netflix.

Dubbing and subtitles may help them in retaining new vocabulary.

Research Questions

How far does watching English TV shows and series help in acquiring advanced vocabulary?

What impact does watching native English shows have on language learners?

Research Design

The study uses a pragmatic approach while adopting mixed method research incorporating qualitative and quantitative analyses. Participants were selected from beginners to advanced level English language learners who watch English programs on Netflix.

Reasons for undertaking this research project

The main reason to opt this project was to highlight the notion that language can be understood well if the learner is immersed completely in the native language. By listening to the same language again and again and by using it in daily life can increase its fluency and can add up to the existing vocabulary of the learner. The world is getting advanced day by day and access to everything has become easier due to digital media

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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therefore it is time to change our learning methods as it is observed that use of multimedia has been introduced in classrooms before the emergence of video streaming (Vander plank, 2016). Therefore, it is time to use new and advanced ways to learn a new language.

Theoretical Framework

This research is based on Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985), which states that language learners can master a new language if the level of input is slightly above their prior knowledge.

Research Methodology and Methods of Research

The study aims to investigate the impact of Netflix on English Language Learner's Vocabulary acquisition by applying mixed method research approach. Mixed method approach is helpful because it helps to gather data more easily and both statistical and thematic data could help analyse the problem in more reliable and valid ways. Method of the research will be the survey questionnaires which will further provide numerical as well as thematic data or personal opinions of the participants.

Population of the study

The population of the present study comprises students of English department who are studying English as a foreign language.

Sampling

Purposive sampling was used to carry out this research. The sample was selected from students ranging from sixth semester to eighth semester, the main reason to select these semesters was that the students from mentioned semesters have an intermediate proficiency level in English which can help them acquire new vocabulary from others platforms as well. A total of 50 students of the research sample took part in the completion of research questionnaires.

Research site

Conducting research in vast geographical area of Pakistan which consists of four provinces (Punjab, Sindh, Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa) and the disputed territory of Kashmir, would have been a difficult and challenging task for the researcher therefore, the area of research was narrowed down to Punjab, which is one of the most populous and largest provinces of Pakistan. Punjab comprises of numerous educational institutions and research sites and it would also have been a tedious task to collect data from all of the institutions so, the research site was again narrowed down to Multan city. Multan also has numerous institutions and it was convenient to collect data from NUML (Multan Campus) because the researcher belongs to this area hence, the research site was easily resourceful.

Construction of instruments

The instrument used in this research was a survey questionnaire including both qualitative and quantitative questions. The quantitative model was introduced by Mujis

Online ISSN

3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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(2004) in his book according to him, the use of questionnaires provides permission to get statistical data that could make it much easier for a researcher in examining and decoding the data and it also allows the researcher to form better observations. Quantitative data were gathered by means of closed-ended questionnaires. Similarly, open-ended questions were also used to fetch qualitative data from the sample.

Reasons for selecting specific research instruments

Quantitative questionnaires provide numerical information which helps in analysing the data quickly through statistical analyses and drawing charts and graphs in Microsoft excel makes it much easier and clearer to analyse while qualitative data provide in depth information which helps in gaining bigger insight of the problem and help in analysing the data more accurately.

Delimitation of the study

This study is narrowed down to English language learners studying in NUML, Multan ranging from 18-25 years while using mixed method approach focusing on variable of vocabulary acquisition and using only Netflix as a streaming platform.

Piloting and Validation

For piloting and validation small-scale research was carried out and online survey forms were disseminated to students of University of Southern Punjab (USP), Multan who were enrolled in English program. A positive response was seen from the students which ensure the validity of this instrument.

Data collection

The data were collected through survey questionnaires which seemed to be very useful in generating accurate results and provided an in-depth analysis of the research questions.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis

Section one: Demographical information

Q1: What is your age?

Under 18

18-25

Figure 1

The figure demonstrates the age group of the students learning English language.

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3007-3197

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3007-3189

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Note. The question seeks the age group of students undertaking this research questionnaire and from the above figure it is evident that 96% of the students were ranging between 18-25 years and only 4% were under 18. This age percentage shows that students are mature enough to understand English broadcasting on streaming platforms.

Q2: What is your level of English proficiency?

Beginner

Intermediate

Advanced

Figure 2: The chart demonstrates the proficiency level of the students learning English language.

Note. The aim of the question was to know the proficiency level of the students that were selected as a sample for this research and it shows that 68% of the students had an intermediate proficiency level. 12% students had beginner and only 20% acquired advanced proficiency level.

Section two:

Netflix watching habits

Q3: How often do you watch Netflix?

Daily

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3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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A few times a week
Once a week
Rarely
Never

Figure 3

The figure displays the students learning English language and the percentage showing how much they watch Netflix

Note. The question seeks how often do the students' Netflix watching routine and the chart above shows that 28% students watch Netflix a few times a week while 12% watch it daily and 40% rarely, 12% once a week and 8% never follows up.

Section three:

Content preference

Q4: What type of content do you watch on Netflix?

Movies

Shows/series

Documentaries

Animated content

Figure 4

The above figure demonstrates the type of content consumed by English language learners on Netflix

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3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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Note. The rationale behind this question was to examine the content watched by the students and the chart demonstrates that 56% students were into tv shows, 24% watched movies and 20% were into animated content.

Section four: Netflix and subtitle use

Q5: Do you use subtitles when watching Netflix in English?

1. Yes, with English subtitles
2. Yes, with subtitles in my native language
3. No, I watch without subtitles

Figure 5

The figure demonstrates subtitle usage in English Language learners when watching Netflix.

Note. The question was designed to investigate subtitle usage while watching Netflix and it is evident from the responses that majority 76% students watched Netflix with subtitles in English and 8% subtitles in native language and 1.4% no subtitle use follows

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3007-3197

Print ISSN

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Q6: Subtitles have made it easier to learn new vocabulary.

Figure 6

The figure shows how English language learners use subtitles in Netflix to acquire new vocabulary.

Note. The chart above demonstrates that 24% students strongly agree that subtitles have made it easier for them to acquire new vocabulary while 60% agree similarly, responses regarding strongly disagree and neutral are tied with 8%.

Section five: Likert Scale

Netflix and vocabulary improvement

How much do you agree with the following statements?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Q7: Watching Netflix has improved my vocabulary.

Figure 7

The above chart demonstrates the percentage of vocabulary improvement after watching Netflix in English Language Learners.

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3007-3197

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3007-3189

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Note. It is evident from the responses that majority of the students agreed that Netflix has improved their vocabulary. 12% students strongly agreed and 44% agreed to this statement while 28% were neutral and 12% strongly disagreed and 8 % disagreed.

Section six

Vocabulary learning through Netflix and using it in daily conversations

Q8: I have learned new words and phrases from Netflix.

Figure 8

Provides information about English language learners and their acquisition of new vocabulary and phrases.

Note. From the above chart and the percentage indicating 56% agreed and 24% strongly agreed accordingly show that students have acquired new phrases and vocabulary after watching Netflix. While the other values show that some strongly disagree, disagree and are neutral in this matter.

Q9: I try to use new words from Netflix in conversations or writings.

Figure 9

The above figure provides the percentage of English language learners and their use of new vocabulary after watching Netflix.

Online ISSN

3007-3197

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3007-3189

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Note. As seen in the chart, it is evident that vocabulary learned from Netflix is used by the students in conversations and writings with a percentage of 44%. While other may disagree or remain neutral in this regard but they are small in proportion.

Section seven

English speaking skills confidence

Q10: Has watching Netflix increased your confidence in using English Vocabulary?

Note. It is evident from the graph that after learning English from Netflix and using it in daily life conversations students had seen boost in their confidence level as well. 28% agreed that their confidence had increased significantly while 52% were less sure about it and 20% had seen no change in their confidence level.

So, from the above analysis it is proved that Netflix is accessed by students and while entertaining themselves they also learn new vocabulary that helps them in real life scenarios.

Qualitative Analysis

Two open-ended questions were given in the survey questionnaire which were as follows:

Q 1: In what ways has watching Netflix in English influenced your vocabulary?

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3007-3197

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The themes generated from the replies of the respondents are:

(i). Confidence in Language use: Many respondents were of the view that after learning vocabulary from Netflix and applying it in their daily life conversations has improved their confidence in English language use and overall, as well. Replies like, *“I used more appropriate words while talking which made me feel confident”* demonstrates that after learning new vocabulary of a foreign language the student feels much more confident in speaking the English language.

(ii). Vocabulary Acquisition:

Responses like, *“Netflix have always had a great impact on my vocabulary, I think I’ve learnt more words this way when I can watch them getting performed”* and *“Watching Netflix has influenced my vocabulary so much that I now try to use those formal words in my writing and speaking and informal ones while having gossips with friends”*, show that students have learnt new vocabulary and they can integrate those new words in their daily life as well.

(iii). Overall Positive Impact:

Response like *“In so many different ways, it makes me feel good when I use new words among people that I learnt from Netflix”*, *“I have learned many words through watching different shows and movies and I could use them in my daily talks if needed, all the English that I have Learned to speak is through talking in English and watching movies/shows”* show that students felt more relaxed and confident after learning and using English which they specifically learned from Netflix.

The abovementioned themes and responses reveal the benefits of using Netflix as a language learning tool and it can help in vocabulary retention, improve speaking skills and increase confidence in speaking English language.

Q 2: Have you noticed any change in your listening and speaking skills (focusing at vocabulary) as a result of watching Netflix? If yes, how?

The themes generated from the replies are:

(i).Listening Improvements

Responses like, *“I feel more at ease at listening English and accent recognition”, “It has improved my comprehension of spoken English”, “I used to watch shows with subtitles but I don’t need them anymore”, “My listening capacity has increased”, and “Yes, my listening skills have improved as I listen to English more and more”*, show that Netflix has surely aided students in listening the native language and making them able to comprehend the language in an efficient way.

(ii).Speaking Improvements

Replies including remarks like, *“I can talk with confidence in English as I watched shows on Netflix”, “Watching Netflix has helped me improve my pronunciation”, “It made me feel more confident as I spoke in English while using advanced vocabulary”* and *“I am better able to communicate with native speakers”* highlights the theme that Netflix plays a pivotal role in improving spoken skills of its viewers.

Majority of the comments were in the favour of Netflix as a language learning tool and a small proportion was confused whether it actually helped them acquire new vocabulary or not.

After analysing the data, it has been observed that students watching Netflix had a positive impact on their English-speaking skills and vocabulary acquisition. Majority

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3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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of the students got to learn new words and phrases and many of them used those new words in their daily conversations which increased their confidence while speaking English. From the above analyses it can be seen that using a streaming platform as a language learning tool may help in learning foreign language.

Conclusion

This study underscores the impact of Netflix on English language learners and their vocabulary. The main aim was to examine whether or not Netflix helps the students in learning vocabulary in English similarly subtitles play a significant role in vocabulary acquisition or not. As stated by Krashen, it is proved that watching Netflix which is slightly beyond the beginner level can improve the vocabulary acquisition of English learners. From the discussions and findings, it was proved that Netflix encourages students to learn new vocabulary and use it in their daily life carrying out fruitful conversations and aids in effective communication. The study was limited to NUML, Multan and only a single platform “Netflix” was discussed throughout the paper. As the paper was directed to the students’ perceptions about Netflix, teachers’ opinion about this platform was not recorded which could have given a comparative analysis. It proves that there is a room for further study. However the available data signified that students were in favour of Netflix and as it helped the students in the learning process pointing at more significantly at their vocabulary acquisition and learning abilities in this particular domain. Conclusively, Netflix should be used in classrooms and teachers should use proper guidelines and use material which is solely related to vocabulary and language learning for the betterment of the students in regard to all skills of language i.e., listening, speaking, reading and writing and thus their relevant sub skills especially vocabulary.

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